

RESULTS OF FLOTATION ENRICHMENT OF WASTE FROM THE COPPER ENRICHMENT FACTORY OF AGMK

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the importance of processing technogenic waste from the mining industry and their negative impact on the environment. Data on the quantitative and qualitative composition of waste from the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine are presented. Granulometric analysis of samples obtained from copper processing plant waste is presented. The results of flotation enrichment of waste under laboratory conditions using various reagents are presented..

A constant increase in the use of natural resources is accompanied by a sharp increase in production waste. In the world, the utilization of technogenic waste from the mining industry is one of the most important problems. On the one hand, technogenic waste contains valuable products containing a large amount of precious and non-ferrous metals, which do not require their extraction, transportation, and grinding, which significantly reduces the cost of their processing. On the other hand, technogenic waste accumulates in landfills, occupies very large areas, and poses a certain degree of ecological danger to the environment [3].

The accumulated amount of accumulated waste in the form of balance and off-balance ore accumulations, dumps, and slag accumulations constitutes one of the types of mineral resources and is classified as technogenic deposits[1].

The current stage of deepening economic reforms requires fundamental structural shifts and the transition of the economy to intensive development. In the complex of urgent tasks to meet the needs of developing sectors of the national economy, great importance is attached to the introduction of a mechanism aimed at the rational use of mineral resources and the processing of technogenic waste. An extensive approach to the development of mineral extraction, i.e., the involvement of increasingly new deposits in the process of exploitation, is currently unacceptable. Such an approach leads to the depletion of many mineral deposits, the

need to use facilities with lower quality raw materials, complex mining and technical conditions of extraction, etc. [2].

Due to the decrease in the content of useful components in raw materials, it is necessary to process more rock mass to obtain the same amount of product, the share of hard-to-enrich ores increases, which leads to an increase in material, labor, and financial costs for the production of the final product and the formation of a large amount of technogenic waste [3].

All this requires the intensification of research, the search for approaches to solving the problem of rational development of mineral resources and the processing of technogenic waste.

As can be seen, reducing the amount of waste through its further processing or use in production, introducing more modern and efficient technologies will contribute to improving the environmental situation, additional savings in resources and energy, as well as more complete development of mineral resources.

The problem of waste utilization from mining enterprises is well known to everyone. This problem is also relevant in our country. The largest enterprises of Uzbekistan - the Navoi and Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combines - are unique in world mining practice both in terms of their production and economic indicators and in terms of the complexity and novelty of the scientific and technical tasks solved during their operation. Despite the advanced technologies used, the mining and metallurgical production of the plants is not waste-free.

Waste from the enrichment of copper-molybdenum ore from the Kalmakyr deposit, i.e., waste generated during the extraction of copper-molybdenum collective concentrate by flotation, occupies a very large area. At the same time, the surrounding areas are flooded, and groundwater is polluted.

The peculiarity of this type of raw material is that it is easily accessible, all flotation waste is located on the surface, densely packed, and, accordingly, does not require large extraction costs, i.e., such a labor-intensive and expensive process as crushing rocks from a monolithic massif (drilling, charging and blasting of blast holes, rock extraction) is eliminated.

Most developed foreign countries have long been pursuing their own policy of mineral resource conservation, intensive involvement in the processing of man-made deposits, destruction of production waste, and development of technologies for processing these wastes. For example, in the USA in 2023, the share of secondary raw materials in the production of non-ferrous metals was: copper - 33%, tungsten - 28%, nickel - 25% [4].

Such a trend in the use of secondary resources is observed not only in the USA, but also in Canada, the Philippines, South Africa, Bulgaria, Russia, and other countries.

Valuable elements in the composition of AMMC MBF waste are copper 1390 g/t, molybdenum 30 g/t, gold 0.33 g/t, silver 1.15 g/t, rhenium 0.037 g/t, bismuth 1.4 g/t, tellurium 0.11 g/t, selenium 3.0 g/t, and palladium 0.46 g/t. When the developed technology is complex, the extraction of metals from technogenic waste in such a composition of valuable components can be economically advantageous.

The mineral composition of MBF waste mainly consists of quartz, feldspars, sericites, and a large amount of dark and secondary minerals. Pyrite is the most common ore mineral in MBF waste. Also, chalcopyrite, sphalerite, galena, molybdenite, and iron oxides were recorded in the concentrates of gravity beneficiation of MBF waste.

To determine the granulometric composition of technogenic waste and the distribution of valuable components by size classes, sieve analysis was carried out.

Table 1
Granulometric composition and distribution of valuable components
by size classes in the dump waste of AMMC MBF

Class size, mm	Exit, %	Composition, %						Distribution, %					
		Fe	Cu	Mo	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Au, g/t	Fe	Cu	Mo	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Au
+1	4.9	7.6	0.29	0.014	60.35	12.03	0.38	5.0	10.2	3.9	4.5	6.0	4.7
-1+0.5	7.9	5.6	0.23	0.014	69.18	10.31	0.33	5.9	13.0	6.2	8.2	8.2	6.6
-0.5+0.315.	20.4	5.1	0.16	0.017	70.59	10.05	0.39	13.8	23.4	19.6	21.7	20.8	20.3
-0.315+0.1.	52.1	7.6	0.11	0.02	67.06	9.65	0.39	52.9	41.1	58.8	52.6	50.9	51.8
-0.1+0.074.	7.1	12.8	0.10	0.017	58.59	8.99	0.52	12.2	5.1	6.8	6.3	6.5	9.4
-0.074+0.	7.6	10.1	0.13	0.011	58.94	9.92	0.37	10.3	7.1	4.7	6.7	7.6	7.2
Preliminary sample	100.0	7.5	0.14	0.018	66.40	9.87	0.392	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

As can be seen from the table. 1, the yield of the +0.1 mm class is significant and ~85%; the -0.074 mm class content in the sample is -7.6%. The most copper-rich classes are greater than 1.0 mm. Metals of other fineness classes are distributed proportionally to the yields. The extraction of metals to the -0.315+0.1 mm class increases in accordance with the product yield. The main content of copper (93%) is divided into the class +0.074 mm.

Flotation studies were conducted in order to completely extract copper, molybdenum, and other precious metals from the tailings of the AKMK copper concentrator.

In the flotation process, a collector - butyl xanthate, kerosene, shale resin, spindle oil - was used as a collector for separating the residual metal content; as a foaming agent - T-92. Unslaked lime was used as a medium regulator.

Flotation was carried out on laboratory flotation machines of the 240-FML brand with a chamber volume of 3 l and FM-2, with a chamber volume of 1 l.

Flotation experiments were conducted according to the scheme in Fig. 1. The sample was ground to a particle size of -0.074 mm and a particle size of 75%. The results of flotation of AKMC MBF dump waste are presented in Table 2. 2.

Figure 1. Scheme of flotation enrichment of AMMC MBF waste

Table 2

Results of flotation of dump tailings of AMMC MBF

No experiment	Products enrichment	Output, %	Composition, g/t						Extraction, %						Reagent consumption, g/t
			Fe,%	Cu,%	Mo	Au	Ag	Re	Fe	Cu	Mo	Au	Ag	Re	
1.	Draft conc.	7.1	11.8	0.99	74.3	2.99	5.37	0.245	15.3	50.4	25.3	58.0	33.3	22.7	Main fleet: Ver. oil - 10, BKK - 40, T-92 - 60; Counter-float: BKK-20, T-92-30
	Industrial product	3.2	20.8	0.33	33.3	1.38	3.65	0.117	12.1	7.5	5.1	12.0	10.2	4.9	
	Waste	89.7	4.5	0.07	16.2	0.12	0.72	0.062	72.6	42.1	69.6	30.0	56.5	72.4	
	Initial	100.0	5.5	0.14	20.9	0.37	1.15	0.077	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
2.	Draft conc.	4.8	23.5	1.14	382.0	4.18	8.07	0.587	21.4	40.1	69.9	34.4	33.9	45.4	Main fleet: Shale resin - 25, BKK - 25, T-92 - 60; Cont. flot.: Shale resin - 10, BKK - 10, T-92 - 30
	Industrial product	3.5	14.7	0.35	49.2	1.38	3.75	0.171	10.0	9.4	6.7	8.4	11.7	9.8	
	Waste	91.7	3.9	0.07	6.7	0.36	0.67	0.030	68.6	49.5	23.5	57.1	54.4	44.8	
	Initial	100.0	5.2	0.13	26.0	0.58	1.13	0.061	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
3.	Draft conc.	4.4	9.0	1.70	489.0	2.02	8.13	1.038	7.7	47.2	76.5	24.6	29.2	46.2	Main fleet: Shale resin - 50, T-92 - 60; Cont. flot.: Shale resin - 25, T-92 - 30
	Industrial product	3.8	5.8	0.41	75.4	1.04	2.97	0.592	4.2	9.8	10.0	10.7	9.1	22.4	
	Waste	91.8	5.0	0.07	4.2	0.26	0.83	0.034	88.1	43.0	13.5	64.6	61.8	31.4	
	Initial	100.0	5.2	0.16	28.3	0.36	1.23	0.099	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
4.	Draft conc.	7.1	24.7	1.12	178.0	2.07	7.31	0.476	33.9	55.9	64.7	41.5	43.5	49.2	Main fleet: BKK-150, P-92-60; Flot counter: BKK-70, T-92-30
	Intermediate product	1.6	8.7	0.36	57.5	0.59	3.27	0.350	2.7;	4.1	4.8	2.7;	4.4	8.2	
	Waste	91.3	3.6	0.06	6.5	0.22	0.68	0.032	63.4	40.0	30.6	55.8	52.1	42.6	
	Initial	100.0	5.2	0.14	19.5	0.35	1.19	0.069	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	
5.	Draft conc.	10.0	14.3	0.87	60.2	2.32	5.21	0.448	28.0	60.8	40.3	60.0	47.5	48.3	Main Fleet: BKK-25, P-92-60; Counter-float: BKK - 12.5, T-92 - 30.
	Intermediate product	2.5	14.7	0.22	32.7	0.70	2.90	0.206	7.1	3.8	5.4	4.5	6.6	5.5	
	Waste	87.5	3.8	0.06	9.3	0.16	0.58	0.049	64.9	35.3	54.3	35.5	45.9	46.2	
	Initial	100.0	5.1	0.14	14.9	0.39	1.10	0.093	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	

As can be seen from the table. As can be seen from Table 2, the yield of the crude concentrate during the flotation of dump tailings of AMMC MBF is 4-10%. In this case, the extraction of copper from the initial technogenic waste into the rough concentrate is in the

range of 40-60%. The copper content in the rough concentrate increases from 0.13-0.16% to 0.87-1.7%.

In the main flotation, with the use of a collector - BKK 25 g/t, a foaming agent T-92 60 g/t, the maximum copper recovery is 60%, while the recovery of molybdenum and gold is 40% and 60%, respectively.

It should be noted that when using shale resin as a collector during the flotation of AMMC MBF waste, the amount of molybdenum in the raw concentrate increases significantly from 382 to 489 g/t, and in parallel, the extraction of molybdenum increases from 70 to 76%.

Based on the obtained results of previously conducted studies, flotation of AMMC MBF waste was carried out with re-treatment of the main flotation concentrate according to the scheme shown in Fig. 2. The reagent consumption in the main flotation was 25 g/t for the collector BKK, 60 g/t for the foaming agent T-92, and 12.5 g/t for the control flotation BKK and 30 g/t for the foaming agent T-92. 3-4.

Figure 2. Scheme of flotation of AMMC MBF waste with re-treatment of the main flotation concentrate

Table 3

Flotation with single re-treatment of AKMK MBF waste dump main flotation concentrate

Enrichment products	Exit product, %	Composition, g/t						Extraction, %					
		Fe, %	Cu	Mo	Au	Ag	Re	Fe	Cu	Mo	Au	Ag	Re
Concentrate 1	1.0	37.3	46991	1099.	8.5	24.0	3900	6.6	27.3	25.8	22.8	15.8	23.7
Concentrate 2	3.5	42.6	14451.	459.	3.5	12.1	1.440	26.6	29.5	38.0	33.4	28.1	30.8

Total concentrate	4.4	40.9	196.30	463.	7.2	14.7	1.540	33.3	56.8	63.8	56.2	44.0	54.4
PromProduct 1	0.9	5.0	2161.	60.	0.6	2.7;	0.189	0.9	1.2;	1.3	1.5;	1.7	1.1
Promproduct 2	2.4	8.8	2553.	103.	0.5	3.3	0.503	3.8	3.6.	5.8	3.2	5.2	7.3
Waste 1	45.6	3.7	671.	12.	0.1	0.8	0.061	31,	18.1	13.5	17.4	23.4	17.2
Waste 2	46.6	3.7	7.35.	14.	0.2	0.8	0.069	31.1	20.3	15.5	21.7	25.7	19.9
Total waste	92.3	4.0	7.30	9.	0.1	0.8	0.053	62.1	38.4	29.0	39.1	49.1	37.2
Initial	100.	5.5	1689.	42.	0.4	1.5;	0.162	100.	100.	100.	100.	100.	100.

As can be seen from the table. As can be seen from Table 3, the recovery of copper and molybdenum into the total concentrate during the flotation of AMMC MBF waste with single purification of the main flotation concentrate is 56.8% and 63.8%, respectively. The amount of copper and molybdenum in the total concentrate increases more than 11 times compared to the initial concentrate and is equal to -1.96%, molybdenum - 463 g/t.

In this case, the recovery of gold, silver, and rhenium into the collective concentrate is 56%, 44%, and 54%, respectively.

Table 4

**Flotation of AMMC MBF waste with double purification
main flotation concentrate**

Enrichment products	Exit product, %	Composition, g/t						Extraction, %					
		Fe, %	Cu	Mo	Au	Ag	Re	Fe	Cu	Mo	Au	Ag	Re
Concentrate 1	1.5;	45.1	32890	795.	7.3	20.2	3.210	12.3	29.2	29.2	29.2	20.9	27.5
Concentrate 2	1.9	44.9	26.031.	583.	5.4	17.7	2.810	15.5	29.2	27.0	27.5	23.1	30.4
Total concentrate	3.4	43.1	27698	618.	7.3	18.8	2390	27.8	58.4	56.2	56.7	44.0	57.9
PromProduct 1	0.4	12.7	3282.	124.	0.7	5.6	0.704	0.9	0.8	1.2;	0.8	1.5;	1.6
Promproduct 2	1.7	7.4	2181.	64.	0.5	3.0	0.197	2.2	2.2	2.6	2.2	3.4	1.9
Promproduct 3	2.7;	20.0	2509.	217.	0.9	4.4	1.190	10.0	4.1	14.6	6.3	8.3	18.7
Waste 1	44.4	3.7	648.	14.	0.2	0.7	0.039	29.8	17.2	15.1	23.1	22.9	10.0
Waste 2	47.5	3.4	613.	9.	0.1	0.6	0.036	29.3	17.4	10.3	10.9	19.8	9.9
Total waste	91.9	3.8	664.	9.	0.1	0.7	0.037	59.1	34.6	25.4	34.0	42.7	19.9
Initial	100.	5.4	1673	40.	0.4	1.4	0.173	100.	100.	100.	100.	100.	100.

As can be seen from the table. The extraction of copper and molybdenum into the total concentrate during the flotation of AMMC MBF waste with double purification of the main flotation concentrate according to the scheme shown in Fig. 2 is 58% and 56%, respectively. At the same time, due to additional purification, the amount of copper and molybdenum in the total concentrate increases more than 15 times compared to the initial and amounts to copper

- 2.8%, molybdenum - 463 g/t. In this case, the extraction of gold, silver, and rhenium into the total concentrate is 56%, 44%, and 57%, respectively.

As a result of the conducted research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. After chemical analysis, the copper content in the waste samples of AMMC MBF averaged 0.139%;

2. In the main flotation, the highest copper recovery is observed with the use of a collector - BKK 25 g/t, a foaming agent - T-92 60 g/t and 60%, with molybdenum and gold recovery of 40% and 60%, respectively.

3. The feasibility of applying the flotation enrichment method of MBF waste and obtaining a low-grade copper concentrate containing copper, molybdenum, gold, silver, and rhenium suitable for processing in the current production of AGMK has been experimentally demonstrated, and the optimal enrichment regimes and efficiency indicators have been determined.

4. The developed technological scheme for processing AMMC MBF waste allows for the separation of metals into a low-grade copper concentrate containing 2.83% copper, 748 g/t molybdenum, 6.2 g/t gold, 21.3 g/t silver, and 3.51 g/t rhenium.

There are two options for further processing of the resulting product:

- increasing the metal content to the maximum permissible concentration for metallurgical processing using the existing enrichment technology;
- based on the experience of world copper concentrate manufacturers (Arthur and Magna factories of the USA and Toledo factory of the Philippines), send the obtained low-grade concentrate containing 2.83% copper to the main plant for combining with the main flotation concentrate in order to increase the metal content..

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